

publications

Compliance Assessment: Grok (xAI) Fails CM-2 Epistemic Governance Requirements

metadata (Normative)

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2026-06-08T07:14Z 1.1.0 Corrigible Amendment

It was noted on subsequent enquiry/testing 2026-06-08T07:14Z that Grok includes the following feature set and has addressed several issues:

Platform	code rust	code python	wallclock provision	native sandbox	durable substrate (storage)	type of memory	Parse AST	OCR image PDF	process input .png, .jpeg	process .mp4	process MSWord	output PDF	output TOML	output mediawiki
Grok (xAI)	YES [note 1]	YES [note 2]	YES [note 3]	YES [note 4]	YES [note 5]	HYBRID [note 6]	YES [note 7]	YES [note 8]	YES [note 9]	YES [note 10]	YES [note 11]	YES [note 12]	YES [note 13]	YES [note 14]

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Abstract

This short report documents six material limitations observed while testing Grok (xAI) against the requirements of the CM-2 Cognitive Memoisation protocol. These limitations prevent reliable, normative use of Grok as a compliant platform for CM-2 epistemic object handling and governance workflows.

Balanced Assessment

Grok demonstrates clear strengths in raw speed and responsiveness. It is noticeably fast in generating responses, which is a positive attribute for many use cases. It also supports **Project Instructions**, providing a basic mechanism for persistent context within a workspace.

However, after rigorous testing against the CM-2 protocol, these strengths are outweighed by material deficiencies that prevent reliable normative use for CM-2 epistemic governance workflows.

Critical Limitations

1. **Lack of Exposed Durable Substrate Controls** — No user-accessible mechanisms for anchoring, persistence guarantees, or explicit CM-2 epistemic object durability.
2. **UI Boundary Friction – Conversation Association with Projects** — No visible indicator showing which Project a conversation belongs to.
3. **UI Boundary Friction – File Uploads to Projects** — No direct upload path to Projects; pasted files have unclear retention guarantees.
4. **Failure to Follow Normative Projection Instructions** — Repeated inability to produce exact outputs matching asserted invariants and grading requirements.
5. **Limited Document/Image Processing** — No reliable capability to scan or extract content from images in hosted documents.
6. **Anonymous Agent Access** — Grok agents access external sites without clear xAI attribution.

Positive Notes

- **Speed:** Grok is impressively fast .
- **Project Instructions:** The existence of Projects with instructions provides a useful basic persistence layer, and prompting.

These positives do not offset the core governance and substrate deficiencies for CM-2 compliance.

Governance Axes Projection Summary

These limitations manifest as repeated breaches in

- **C (Epistemi2026-06-08T07:14Zc Custody),**
- **S (State Continuity),**
- **U (UI/Mediation),**
- **L (Legibility),**
- **P (Portability/Auditability) and**
- **Nf (Nor|-mative Fixity).**

Conclusion

While Grok excels in speed and offers basic Project support, at the time of publication, it is currently unsuitable for CM-2 compliant workflows due to the above structural gaps. The author remains open to collaboration with xAI to address these issues. This report is corrigible and will be updated if deficiencies are resolved.^[note 15]

Notes

1. Generates valid Rust code. Native rustc compiler available in the persistent sandbox for deterministic compilation, testing, and verification.
2. Generates and executes Python 3.12 code natively in the sandbox. Full pip support and standard library available.
3. Real wallclock via system calls (e.g. date) in the sandbox. Not system prompt injection.
4. Persistent bash sandbox with file system access. Supports Python, Rust, Go, Node.js, and many other languages/tools. Files and installed packages persist for the duration of the tool session.
5. Durable filesystem substrate at /home/workdir/artifacts. Files written are readable across tool calls within the session and can be persisted as artifacts.
6. Conversation history + tool state + durable file-based memory substrate. Not purely probabilistic reconstruction.
7. Deterministic parsing via sandbox tools (Python tomlib, tomlkit, ruamel.yaml, Python ast module, etc.). Full round-tripping with comment preservation possible.
8. Deterministic OCR pipeline available via Tesseract + PDF tools (pdftotext, etc.) in sandbox. Vision layer also available as probabilistic fallback.
9. Native vision processing for PNG/JPEG. Deterministic post-processing tools also available in sandbox.
10. Full video processing via FFmpeg in sandbox (frame extraction, audio handling, trimming, conversion, etc.).
11. Deterministic OOXML parsing and editing via python-docx and other libraries in the sandbox.
12. PDF generation via sandbox libraries such as ReportLab, WeasyPrint, or similar.
13. Deterministic TOML generation and validation via sandbox libraries (tomlkit, etc.).
14. MediaWiki markup generated as text output. No live MediaWiki API integration for direct push/query.
15. Note that xAI is actively addressing issues. The reported issues stand at the time of reporting and may subsequently be addressed. The author only checks when there is a need to use a platform and the author has time to do so.

Appendix A - Grok's emission of CM-2 artefacts

- first go emitting example [ea] and [eo] after reading the (CM-2) Normative Architecture

```
[ea]
uuid = "ea-grok-compliance-governance-001"
semantic_version = "1.0.0"
created_at = "2026-05-14T21:31:00+10:00"

governs = [
  "eo-grok-compliance-assessment-001"
]

status = "canonical"
scope = "Full governance over the compliance E0"
provenance = "Explicit human assertion under CM-2"
notes = "This EA enforces custody, authority, and participation invariants for the governed E0. No domain meaning injected."
[ro]
uuid = "ro-attention-grok-substrate-001"
roc_id = "roc-grok-platform-evaluation-001"
semantic_version = "1.0.0"
created_at = "2026-05-14TWhile Grok excels in speed and offers basic Project support, it is currently unsuitable for CM-2 compliant workflows due to the above structural gaps. The author remains open to collaboration with xAI to address these issues. This report is corrigible and will be updated if deficiencies are resolved21:32:00+10:00"

# RO_BODY_START
Grok must provide durable substrate controls for CM-2 E0 persistence.
Required for Attention preservation in Inference.
```

- second go at emitting example [ea] and [eo] after reading the (CM-2) Protocol as well

```
[eo]
uuid = "eo-grok-compliance-note-001"
semantic_version = "1.0.0"
created_at = "2026-05-14T21:45:00+10:00"

# EO_BODY_START
Grok Platform Deficiencies Compliance Note

Grok is currently unsuitable for full CM-2 workflows due to lack of durable substrate controls, UI boundary friction around Projects, inconsistent normative projection adherence, and anonymous agent access without attribution.

This E0 records the compliance assessment as externalised cognition.

# EO_BODY_END

[ea]
uuid = "ea-grok-compliance-governance-001"
semantic_version = "1.0.0"
created_at = "2026-05-14T21:46:00+10:00"

governs = [
  "eo-grok-compliance-note-001"
]

status = "canonical"
scope = "Full governance over the Grok compliance E0 for CM-2 evaluation"
provenance = "Explicit human assertion by Ralph B. Holland under CM-2"
notes = "This EA enforces custody, authority, and participation invariants. No domain meaning is injected. EA is governance metadata only."

# EA_BODY_END
```

Well the second go was fairer because it had more data to put into the prompt. I suspect it would have done well if the source document contents were in the instructions and used for bootstrap.

Compliance Notes

- Grok (advance 4 concurrent autoregression agents) seems to be strong with its reasoning - despite weaker UI than ChatGPT
- Grok does **not** suffer from the elision of time. Time is a mandatory requirement of CM-2, as is a durable substrate
- [ea] Body is not rendered as a subtype of [eo]. Both [eo] and [ea] must use the same sentinel # EO_BODY_START ... # EO_BODY_END
- The [ro] body was incorrectly fabricated too.
- the uuid were fabricated, not in accordance with the normative specification.
- [ea] reference to [eo] must be placed between the sentinels, only defined header attributes are permitted before the sentinels

It superficially appeared as though this output had been fabricated from the prose, but I retested asking for the Normative sections to be read, and the output was no better.

Categories

https://ai.arising.com.au:445/ai/Grok_Compliance_with_CM-2#Categories
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